

STUDY ON COMPOSITES WITH THERMOPLASTIC MATRICES III.
CONTINUOUS CARBON FIBER REINFORCED CHINA-MADE HIGH-PERFORMANCE
RESINS*

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Their intrinsic high performance, design flexibility and cost-effective continuous processing provide the high-performance thermoplastic composites with the considerable economy of production and make them an alternation to thermoset systems. Composites with high-performance thermoplastic matrix have been reported in U.S.A. in 1970's. Since 1970's the heat-resistant high-performance thermoplastic resins have been developed in this institute. The composites based on those thermoplastic resins are also developing now in the institute. In this work the properties of the composites with those China-made high-performance thermoplastic matrices were reported.

Thermoplastic matrices used here are amorphous poly (phenylene ether ketone) with cardo group (PEK-C), polyether sulphone with cardo group (PES-C) and polyetherimide (PEI-100). The properties of them are listed in Table 1-3.

The prepreg sheets were made by solution coating with China-made carbon fiber with 2.5 GPa in tensile strength and 1.5% in break strain. Unidirectional laminated plates were molded by compression forming of the prepreg sheets at temperature higher than T_g of matrix resins. The laminated number of prepreg sheets is 12 and the thickness of laminated plate is about 2.2 mm.

By using Instron Universal Testing Machine model 1121 the static mechanical properties of the composites were measured according to the Chinese Standard Testing Measurement, i.e. GB 3357-82 for interlaminar shear strength and GB 3356-82 for flexural properties. DuPont 9900 Dynamic Mechanical Analyzer was used for dynamic mechanical properties of the composites.

Table 4 gives the mechanical properties at room temperature of unidirectional carbon filament composites. Although the flexural properties are excellent, the interlaminar shear strength is not as good as expected. One of the reasons is that epoxy sizings on the surface of carbon fiber was not removed, which affected adhesion between fiber and resin. Good retention of flexural storage modulus is also shown by those composites (Table 5).

Although the data shown above are preliminary results and composites processing has not yet been optimized, the thermoplastic resins used in this work have shown potentiality as matrices for the advanced thermoplastic composites.

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Table 1 Properties of PEK-C

Appearance	Dark amber
Density (kg/m ³)	1309
Tg (°C)	228
Temperature of weight loss 5% (°C)	490
Weight loss at 400 °C (%)	0
at 500 °C (%)	5
Tensile strength (MPa)	98.1
Elongation (%)	100
Impact strength (kJ/m ²)	45
Dielectric constant at 50 Hz, 200 °C	3.0
Dielectric factor at 50 Hz	1.4×10^{-3}
Volume resistance Ω -cm	1.43×10^{18}
Surface resistance Ω	3.0×10^{17}

Table 2 Properties of PEI-100

Appearance	Amber to dark brown
Density (kg/m ³)	1365
Combustion	self-extinguishing
Temperature of decomposition (°C)	
in N ₂	460
in air	450
Heat distortion temperature under load of 1.81 MPa (°C)	232
Weight loss at 220 °C for 750 hrs	< 1%
Coefficient of linear expansion (1/°C)	2.7×10^{-5}
Tensile strength (MPa)	108
Flexural strength at yield point (MPa)	163
Compression strength (MPa)	150
Izod impact strength (kJ/m ²)	
original	152
after aging at 220°C for 750 hrs	142
Friction coefficient	0.24

Table 3 Properties of PES-C

Tg (°C)	260
Weight loss at 250 °C, 400 hrs (%)	0.5
Tensile strength (MPa)	102.6
Tear strength (MPa)	23.5
Dielectric factor at 300 Hz, r.t.	1.5×10^{-3}
145°C	2.8×10^{-3}
Dielectric constant at 300 Hz, r.t.	3.38
145°C	3.33
Volume resistance Ω -cm	3.1×10^{16}
Hydrolysis resistance at 200 °C, 4 hrs	
appearance	unchanged
weight loss (%)	+0.6

Table 4 Mechanical properties of unidirectional carbon filament composites at room temperature

Matrix	PEK-C	PES-C	PEI-100
Fiber content (vol%)	63	53	69
Void content (%)	-0.3	1.2	1.6
Density (kg/m ³)	1595	1522	1611
Flexural strength (MPa)	1246	867	1200
Flexural modulus (GPa)	131	95	116
Interlaminar shear strength (MPa)	54	50	45
Impact strength (kJ/m ²) (Charpy, unnotched)	145	116	123

Table 5 Elevated temperature mechanical properties of unidirectional carbon filament composites

Matrix		Interlaminar shear strength (MPa)	Flexural storage modulus (GPa)	
			longitudinal	tranverse
PEK-C	r.t.	54	38.4	9.01
	150°C	39.6	37.2	8.21
	200°C	—	27.1	5.18
PES-C	r.t.	50	42.5	5.89
	150°C	41.2	41.9	5.43
	200°C	33.9	41	5.19
PEI-100	r.t.	45	53.1	5.8
	150°C	40	49.8	5.05
	200°C	27.1	45	4.53